

CURRENT STATE OF DEVELOPMENT OF FOREIGN PSYCHOLOGY**Mamayusupova Iroda Khamidovna**

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Abstract. *In the article foreign psychologists S. Hall, A. Gesell, E. Spranger, Sh. According to the instructions of Buhler, V. Stern, J. Piaget, L. S. Vygotsky, A. Freud, Eric Erickson analyzed the conditions of development. It was revealed that the relationship and connection of mental processes, mental states and mental characteristics constitute the psychological structure of a person.*

Keywords: *Mental processes, mental states, mental characteristics, personality, psychological structure, teenager, character, paradoxical, ambivalent.*

СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗАРУБЕЖНОЙ ПСИХОЛОГИИ

Аннотация. *В статье зарубежные психологи С. Холл, А. Гезелл, Э. Шпрангер, Ш. По указаниям Бюлера, В. Штерна, Ж. Пиаже, Л. С. Выготского, А. Фрейда, Эрика Эриксона проанализировали условия развития. Выявлено, что взаимосвязь и связь психических процессов, психических состояний и психических характеристик составляют психологическую структуру человека.*

Ключевые слова: *Психические процессы, психические состояния, психические характеристики, личность, психологическая структура, подросток, характер, парадоксальный, амбивалентный.*

INTRODUCTION

Each person has certain social relations, characteristic of his age, and is the object of many economic, political, legal and moral influences exerted on him by society. The character, temperament, abilities of a person are manifested in work and life when he experiences mental processes. Therefore, the interrelation and connection of mental processes, mental states and mental characteristics make up the psychological structure of a person. Unfortunately, sometimes, when we think about a person, we have to think about health, illness and a third state, which is neither health nor illness.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

S. Hall (1940) in his theory of recapitulation of adolescent humanity. coincides with the romantic era of the history of development and emphasizes that this is the stage between childhood and adulthood. He explains the situations of paradox and ambivalence in the character of a teenager, drawing attention to the fact that his activity is dominated by extreme activity, joy is

replaced by sadness, self-confidence is replaced by shyness, egoism is replaced by altruism, spirituality. pretension is replaced by low excitability, the desire for communication is expressed by pessimism, etc., which is associated with a crisis of self-awareness. That is, he proves that overcoming it causes a "sense of individuality". American psychologist A. Gesell (1880-1861) relies on a biological model of development similar to S. Hall's and believes that renewal, integration and balance take place in it. "Growth" and "development" are synonymous for Gesell, and he means the process of progressive differentiation and integration of behavior. While acknowledging cultural influence, Gesell emphasizes that culture directs, but does not cause, the stages and trends of development. A. Gesell is interested in the question of how the development process and personality traits are reflected in the behavior of the individual. Another major researcher of adolescence, the German philosopher and psychologist E. Spranger (1924), explained that adolescence lasts until the age of 14-21 for girls and 13-19 for boys, with its first stage corresponding to the age of 14-17, when an escape from childhood occurs. In his cultural-psychological concept of adolescence, he distinguishes three types of development. The first type is a tense, crisis, stormy night, and the teenager feels his second birth, as a result of which a new "I" is born. The second type - in the adult life of the teenager, there is a sense of calm, peace and continuity, and deep and serious changes in his personality do not occur. The third type is a stage of the development process, at which the teenager persistently overcomes his internal experiences and crises, forms and educates himself with active self-awareness. Thus, E. Spranger proved that the founders of this age are the awareness of one's own individuality, the emergence of reflection, the disclosure of the "I", and laid the foundations for a systematic study of the worldviews, values and self of the teenager. - awareness. Sh., who called adolescence the period of puberty. The biological essence of this period is revealed in the works of Bühler. Puberty is a period of biological growth, when puberty ends, but physical development continues. He calls the stage before puberty human childhood, and the end of this period - adolescence. S. Bühler divides the period of puberty into two: mental and physical periods. External and internal stimuli that influence the behavior of a teenager can destroy his self-satisfaction and calmness and encourage him to search for the opposite sex. Biological maturation makes him inquisitive, and his "I" feels the desire to meet "He". That is, S. Bühler tries to distinguish mental puberty from physical. According to him, physical maturity is on average 14-16 years for boys and 13-15 years for girls. Of course, such differences take into account the influence of urban and rural areas, individual countries and even climate. S. G. Getzer, based on Bühler's research, emphasizes that the negative stage of puberty turns into a positive stage between 13 and 16 years, when a person indulges in thoughts, feels the need for a close friend, tries to "look for a friend".

E. V. Stern, one of Spranger's followers, considers adolescence to be one of the main stages of personality formation. V. Stern tries to explain the proverb "If you show me your friend, I will tell you who you are", meaning "Tell me about the most valuable experience in your life, and I will tell you who you are." Because his personality is formed under the influence of experiences that make up the content of a teenager's life. Valuable experience helps to divide his personality into types. V. According to Stern, the transition is not only an ideal and direction of aspirations, feelings and thoughts, but also a specific figure (image) of action. He calls this a situation between childhood games and responsible activities of adult life and calls it "serious games". He emphasizes that serious games allow a teenager to set goals, express his attitude to various interests and overcome hesitations in comparative analysis, strengthen his will.

Another scientific concept belongs to J. Piaget, who tries to explain the last fundamental decentration with 11-12 years to 14-15 years, i.e. the liberation of the child's field of perception from its object and the beginning of the perspective on how to change the world in it. In his opinion, at this age a life program is drawn up (hypodeductively, i.e. with the help of thinking) and the formation of personality is completed.

Thus began a new direction in the study of the problems of adolescence.

CONCLUSION

By observing the behavior of children of different ages, he creates a generalized idea of the stages and cycles of adolescent development. In this statement, he describes the behavior considered normal for each stage in chronological order. No matter how important education and acculturation are for a person, he can never outgrow the influence of growing up. Adolescence is considered to be a period of destruction and loss of old interests and the emergence of new interests with a new biological basis. The transition to a new phase of development occurs in the form of a "normative crisis", which looks like a pathological condition, but in fact means the difficulties of normal growth.

The teenager with his plan and program enters adult society, where he encounters various obstacles, in a sense becomes attached to them and experiences the process of socialization.

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